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CLINICAL STUDY FOR THE EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTS OF IRSALE ALAQ (LEECH THERAPY) IN ECZEMA

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ABSTRACT

Nare Farsi (Eczema) is a chronic inflammatory skin disease posing a significant burden on health-care resources and patients' quality of life. It is a complex disease with a wide spectrum of clinical presentations and combinations of symptoms. *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) affects up to 20% of children and up to 3% of adults. First manifestations of *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) usually appear early in life and often precede other allergic diseases such as asthma or allergic rhinitis. Individuals affected by *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) usually have genetically determined risk factors affecting the skin barrier function or the immune system. However, genetic mutations alone might not be enough to cause clinical manifestations of *Nare Farsi* (Eczema), and it is merely the interaction of a dysfunctional epidermal barrier in genetically predisposed individuals with harmful effects of environmental agents which leads to the development of the disease. *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) has been described as an allergic skin disease, but today, the contribution of allergic reactions to the initiation of *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) is challenged, and it is proposed that allergy is rather a consequence of *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) in subjects with a concomitant underlying atopic constitution. This trial was conducted to evaluate the effect of Leech therapy on *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) at RRIUM, Srinagar, Jammu and Kashmir. The results showed a significant improvement in sign and symptoms with ($p < 0.01$).

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INTRODUCTION

Nare Farsi (Eczema), is a common chronic or recurrent inflammatory skin disease and affects 15–20% of children [1] and 1–3% of adults worldwide. It is characterized by acute flare-ups of eczematous pruritic lesions over dry skin. *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) usually starts in early childhood and may represent the initial step of the so-called ‘atopic march’ (Fig. 1) Which represents the natural history of atopic manifestations, characterized by a typical sequence of atopic diseases in childhood preceding the development of other allergic disorders later in life [2–4]. Fifty percent of all those with *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) develop other allergic symptoms within their first year of life and probably as many as 85% of the patients experience an onset below 5 years of age. Patients usually outgrow the disease in late childhood as around 70% of the patients with a disease onset during childhood have a spontaneous remission before adolescence. However, early childhood *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) is often the initial indication that a child may later develop asthma and/or allergic rhinitis (hay fever) [5]. Symptoms of *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) include patches of skin that are red or brownish, dry, cracked or scaly skin and itchy skin, especially at night. In infants, eczema usually appears as tiny bumps on the cheeks, while older children and adults often experience rashes on the knees or elbows (often in the folds of the joints), on the backs of the hands or on the scalp. *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) poses a significant burden on health-care resources [6–8] and patients’ quality of life (mainly because of sleep deprivation due to itchiness, employment loss, time to care and financial costs) [9–12]. As a consequence, there has been a heightened interest in the identification of environmental risks and protective factors. Epidemiology The prevalence of *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) is estimated to be 15–20% in children and 1–3% in adults, and the incidence has increased by 2- to 3-fold during the past decades in industrialized countries. Some of the most valuable *Nare Farsi* (Eczema) prevalence and trend data have come from the International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC). This is the biggest (close to 2 million children in 100 countries) and only allergy study that has taken a truly global approach. The strength of the study is the use of a uniformly validated methodology allowing a direct comparison of results between pediatric populations all over the world.

Nar-e-farsi is a dermatological disorder which is well known since Greeco-Arab period. Unani Physicians not only described the normal structure and functions of skin but also mentioned the etiology, pathophysiology, clinical pictures, line of treatment (Usool-e-Ilaaj) and management of various skin disease. Unani scholars have described the Nar-e-farsi (Eczema) in detail along with meaning, etiology (Asbaab), pathophysiology (Maahiyat), Aqsam (Types), clinical pictures (Alamat) and management (Ilaaj) [13] According to unani philosophy Nare Farsi results from admixing of safra wa sauda Mohratiqua (Abnormal yellow and black bile) with blood. These abnormal humors alter the mizaj of blood as well as the organs gets nourishment from it. Body’s corrective force (Tabiyat) expels the abnormal humors towards skin, because expelled humors are highly irrigative and hot, hence they cause itching and burning sensation. The viscous part of these humors may conclude as scale or crusts and diluted hot part accumulated as vesicles [14-17]. Various therapies have been used for this clinical condition but all are with poor response and limitations. Treatment with Unani medicine is considered the best because of better acceptability, safety and efficacy, potency, low cost with least or no side effects.

According to the Unani system of medicine, leech therapy works on the principles of *Tanqiyae Mawad* (Evacuation of Morbid Humors) and *Imalae Mawad* (Diversion of humors). *Tanqiyae Mawad* means the resolution and excretion of morbid humors and excess fluids from the body, thereby maintaining the homeostasis in the quality and quantity of body humors, which are actually responsible for the maintenance of normal health. *Imalae Mawad* refers to the diversion of the morbid fluids from the site of affected organ to the site where from it is easily expelled from the body tissues. Based on this holistic approach, leech therapy was selected for the management of *Nare farsi* (Atopic Eczema) in this study. The effectiveness of this therapy may also be attributed to the *Mokhaddir* (Sedative) and *Muhallil* (Anti-inflammatory) actions of saliva of leeches.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Plan of the Basal Study

The patients fulfilling the diagnostic criteria were selected for the study and interviewed thoroughly along to obtain detailed information about the patient as well as the disease and collected in different data viz-

1. Demographic profile
2. Clinical profile

Duration of treatment

The total duration of treatment was fixed for 1 month with the regular 7 days follow-ups. Sample size is 30. The patients are involved in the study after obtaining informed consent.

Criteria for diagnosis of Eczema

- ✓ Itching
- ✓ Burning sensation
- ✓ erythema
- ✓ Scaling
- ✓ Cracking
- ✓ Crusting
- ✓ Swelling
- ✓ Papules
- ✓ Weeping and
- ✓ Oozing of the skin

Inclusion Criteria

1. The patients were clinically diagnosed according to signs and symptoms.
2. Age-20 to 60 yrs.
3. Sex- Either Male or Female.
4. Marital status- Either Married or Unmarried.
5. Socioeconomic status- All classes.

Exclusion criteria

1. Patients having age less than 20 yrs. and more than 60 yrs.
2. Patients having inconclusive diagnosis.
3. Patient with systemic illness like HTN, DM, Impaired Renal or Hepatic functions. Patients with other skin diseases like Psoriasis, Ictheosis etc. Allergic Dermatitis.

Criteria for Efficacy

Relieved: 50% relief in sign and symptoms.

Partially relieved: 25% relief in sign and symptoms.

No response: any relief in sign and symptoms.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

A cross-sectional study was conducted on 30 eligible patients to assess effect of Leech therapy in Eczema. The observations and results are as under:

Table: 1 Distribution of participant on the basis of age.

Age group(in years)	No. of patients
20-30	05
31-40	15
41-50	06
51-60	04
Total	30

Inference: Majority of the patients were lie in the age group of 31-40years.

Graph 1: Distribution of participant on the basis of age.

Table: 2 Distribution of participant on the basis of sex.

SEX	No. of patients
Male	22
Female	08
Total	30

Graph 2: Distribution of participant on the basis of sex.

Table 3: Distribution of participants according to SES.

SES	No. of patients
lower class	17
Middle class	10
Higher class	03
Total	30

Inference: Majority of the participants were from middle class.

Graph 3: Distribution of participants according to SES.

Table 4:- Distribution of patients according to their Mizaj.

Mizaj	No. of patients
Damavi	03
Balghami	7
Safravi	06
Saudavi	14
Total	30

Graph 4:- Distribution of patients according to their Mizaj.

Table 5: Response of treatment.

Response of treatment	No. of patients
Relieved	14
Partially relieved	10
No response	6

Graph no 5: Response of treatment.

DISCUSSION

In this clinical trial out of 30 patients 22 patients were Male and 08 were female. Males are affected more than female. This finding was in accordance with the survey of Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Its prevalence was slightly higher in the age group of 31-40 years i.e 15 cases and least in the age group of 51-60 years i.e 05 cases. {fig 1,table 1,fig2, table2} As per SES most of cases belongs to lower class family[17] cases{fig3,table 3}. According to the *Mizaj* (Temperament) out of 40 patients 03 patients were of *Damvi*, 07 patients were of *Balgami*, 06 patients were of *Safravi* and 14 patients were of *Saudavi mizaj*. It means Atopic Eczema is more common in the patients with *Saudavi mizaj* and least in *Damavi mizaj* (Figure 4).

Therapeutic response of leech therapy showed that out of 30 cases, 14 cases were relieved from their symptoms, 10 were partially relieved and 06 patient had no response. Results were assessed by using the Student 't' test and The result of the study showed a significant improvement in sign and symptoms with ($p < 0.001$). {Table 5, Fig 5}

CONCLUSION

The present study revealed that Leech therapy is safe, effective and of short duration therapy ($P < 0.01$). No recurrence or exacerbation was reported by any patients after completion of trial up to one month of follow up. No patients reported any adverse event throughout the trial and follow up duration. Eczematous signs and symptoms were improved.

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Conflict of Interest: No any.

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